

Oral communication ; Thématique : *Alimentation, nutrition et santé*.

Risk mapping for residues of medroxyprogesterone acetate in pigs, Madagascar

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Residues of synthetic anabolic hormones were detected in sows at slaughterhouses in Madagascar. Previous results show that medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA) was the only synthetic hormone detected and that positive samples were observed in 87.5% of the surveyed regions. This contamination of pork was associated with the informal and illegal distribution of injectable contraceptive hormones initially used for humans. Audit and control measures have been implemented by Madagascar's Ministry of Health for the distribution system of medicinal products, but no action was conducted in the livestock sector. The global misuse of MPA in pig farms was unclear whereas it seems to be frequent. No recent data exist about the occurrence of contaminated meat in Malagasy regions. Under the framework of the INTERREG-V Qualinnov2 project, firstly, we aim at identifying the areas where the contamination may be a priori the more frequently observed (risk mapping) before, in a second phase, implementing a targeted survey in slaughterhouses to investigate the occurrence of contaminated meat by rapid detection test (ELISA). Our communication describes the method for risk mapping and our preliminary results.

We used a Spatial Multicriteria Evaluation (GIS/MCE) method to produce risk maps for MPA contamination in pigs at the country level. This method transforms and combines geographical data and value judgments to obtain appropriate and useful information for decision making. Our GIS/MCE model was developed using data describing the drug supply chains in the veterinary and human sectors, the Malagasy pig population as a proxy for the demand for veterinary drugs by pig farmers, and various social, educational and economical parameters as a proxy for the potential use of illegal products in livestock.

A preliminary maps built between May and December 2019 show that Analamanga, Bongolava, and Vakinankaratra regions are potentially at higher risk. These first evaluations seem to be consistent with the literature but the final predicted risk map will be confirmed and validated with observed data and biological samples. Consequently, biological samples will be collected on pig carcasses in slaughterhouses during 2020 and tested for MPA by ELISA technic; ELISA-positive samples will be then confirmed by GC-MS methods.

Keywords : Risk mapping, medroxyprogesterone acetate, pigs, Madagascar